

FEAST

Mapping and
identification
of policies for
healthy and
sustainable
food systems

Report

D3.3

www.feast2030.eu

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

FEAST is co-funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101060536. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

UK participant in FEAST (Good Food Oxfordshire) is supported by Innovate UK grant number 10041509 and the Swiss participant in FEAST (FiBL) is supported by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) under contract number 22.00156.

Start Date 01/07/2022, End Date 30/06/2027

Cite as: S Harrington, J., Steele, M., Hussey, S., Peralta, H., Kristen, M., O Connor, N., Lorenzo, N., Dastoum, S., Vandevijvere, S., Tonello, S., Hickersberger, M., Forrer, F., Chirilli, C., Bairati, L., Ferreira, J., Barelds, L., & Jani, A. (2025).

FEAST - Mapping and identification of policies for healthy and sustainable food systems.

Zenodo. FEAST project - Food systems that support transitions to hEalthy And Sustainable dieTs.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15512511>

This document is shared under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0).

Food systems that support transitions to hEalthy And Sustainable dieTs

Deliverable Name	Mapping and identification of policies for healthy and sustainable food systems
Description	Mapping and identification of policies for healthy and sustainable food systems to enable consumers, especially vulnerable groups, to consume healthy/sustainable diets
Work Package (WP)	Mapping and Monitoring factors that shape food environments (WP3)
Deliverable Related No.	D3.3
Lead Beneficiary	University College Cork (UCC)
Type	R
Dissemination Level	Public (PU)
Due Date and Project Month	June 30, 2025 / Month 36
Author(s)	Harrington Janas M. (UCC), Steel Margaret (UCC), Hussey Shannen (UCC), Peralta Herrera Kristen Massiel (UCC), O Connor Nora, Lorenzo Nora (Sciensano), Dastoum Sara (Sciensano), Vandevijvere Stefanie (Sciensano), Tonello Samuele (EuroHealthNet), Hickersberger Michaela (ÖKO), Forrer Flavia (ÖKO), Chirilli Chiara (USG), Bairati Lorenzo (USG), Ferreira Joana, Barelds Leonie (LBI), Jani Anant (UKH)
Revision	See Table History of Changes

Date June 20th, 2025

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Key Facts	3
ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS	4
1. Introduction	5
2. Aims.....	7
3. Methods	7
4. Findings	9
4.1 Food-EPI Policy Domains.....	9
4.1.1 Food composition	9
4.2.2 Food Labelling	9
4.2.3. Food provision	10
4.2.4. Food Promotion	10
4.2.5. Food in Retail	11
4.2.6. Food Trade and Investment.....	12
4.2.7. Food Prices.....	13
4.3 Food EPI Infrastructure Support Domains	15
4.3.1 Leadership.....	15
4.3.2 Governance	16
4.3.3 Monitoring and Intelligence.....	16
4.3.4 Funding and Resources	17
4.3.5 Platforms for Interaction	18
4.3.6 Health in-All Policies	19
5. Implications for Food Environment Transformation	22
5.1 Opportunities for Nutrition–Sustainability Synergies.....	23
5.2 Addressing Structural Trade-offs	23
6. Conclusion.....	24
References	25

HISTORY OF CHANGES

Table 1 Document history of changes

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
Version	Publication Date	Changes
1.0	30.06.2025	
2.0	20.04.2026	Correction of the incorrect designation “Lead Beneficiary”: Change from the Louis Bolk Institute (LBI) to University College Cork (UCC). The list of acronyms and abbreviations has been expanded to include the names of the partners.

Key Facts

Action Number: 101060536

Action Acronym: FEAST

Action title: Food systems that support transitions to hEalthy And Sustainable dieTs

Date: 30.06.2025

Version: 1.0

ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

Table 2 List of acronyms and abbreviations

AVMS	Audio Visual Media Services
CAP	Common Agriculture Policy
ECHI	European Core Health Indicators
EHIS	European Health Information Survey
EU	European Union
Food EPI	Food Environment Policy Index
FOPL	Front of Pack Labelling
NCD	Non-communicable diseases
NOPA	Nutrition Obesity and Physical Activity EURO NCD Database
Öko	Ökosoziales Forum Österreich & Europa
UCC	University College Cork
USG	Università degli Studi di Scienze Gastronomiche
WCRF	World Cancer Research Fund

1. Introduction

The overarching aim of the FEAST project is to make it easy for every person in Europe to eat a delicious, healthier and more sustainable diet. Work Package 3 contributes to this aim by mapping and monitoring factors that shape food environments. It is well established that dietary behaviours are shaped not solely by individual choices, but by a complex interplay of factors—including social, cultural, and environmental influences. (1-4). Among these, the food environment plays a particularly significant role. (5) The food environment encompasses the physical (e.g. food availability, quality, marketing), economic (e.g. food prices), policy (e.g. regulations and food policies), and sociocultural (e.g. norms and beliefs) conditions that affect individuals' food choices and nutritional outcomes. (6) In many European Member States, food environments often make healthy and sustainable choices more difficult instead of making them easier. (7)

In FEAST Task 3.1, we examined the commitments and practices of the food industry in relation to key domains such as reformulation and marketing. We found that industry falls well short of best practice in these domains (further information can be found at: [10.5281/zenodo.10551886](https://zenodo.org/record/10551886); [10.5281/zenodo.14860170](https://zenodo.org/record/14860170); [10.5281/zenodo.14329563](https://zenodo.org/record/14329563); [10.5281/zenodo.14860345](https://zenodo.org/record/14860345)). This is consistent with previous evidence showing that the market has largely failed to deliver optimal public health outcomes, as commercial interests have often taken precedence over public health goals. (8) To reverse current trends and foster supportive food environments, governments must take decisive action and implement comprehensive policies aimed at preventing and addressing diet-related overweight, obesity, and NCDs. (9) Governments, (at European, national and local level) can introduce measures to directly change the food environment, for example by regulating food marketing, zoning, taxing unhealthy/unsustainable food and making healthy foods, like fruits and vegetables, more affordable (10-13).

In Task 3.2, we mapped stakeholders and policies at local (city, region or municipality as appropriate) level. We found that local stakeholders and policymakers are committed to ensuring access to healthy and sustainable diets, but they sometimes lack the authority or the resources to make the necessary changes in food environments. This shows the importance of considering all levels of policymaking, and how they work together. Article 168 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union stipulates that a high level of human health protection must be ensured in the definition and implementation of all EU policies and activities. (14) However, the responsibility for defining health policy and organizing and delivering health services and medical care primarily lies with the Member States. (15) The European Commission's Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety (DG SANTE) supports Member States in their efforts through a variety of mechanisms, including legislative proposals, financial support, coordination, facilitation of knowledge exchange among countries and health experts, and health promotion initiatives. While one of DG SANTE's core missions is to "improve and protect human health and monitor (citizens) food making sure it is safe," EU-level action is largely limited to incentive-based measures—such as raising awareness to prevent non-communicable diseases (NCDs), promoting healthy lifestyles, and fostering cooperation. (16) A snapshot of Member States' progress in implementing the WHO European Food and Nutrition Action Plan 2015–2020 indicates that more ambitious policies and their associated implementation are needed for countries to meet global nutrition targets. (17)

In Task 3.3, we developed a methodology to work with vulnerable populations in communities to co-design solutions that provide access to healthy diets from sustainable food systems. The set up for the workshop is inspired by the model of Positive Health and Living Environment, also leveraging important elements of Group Model Building, taking into account the barriers and facilitators to

consuming healthier and more sustainable diets based on individual factors, social structures and local environments. Different tools are part of the workshop : i) graphs over time, which captures the community's understanding of an issue; ii) brainstorming on qualities, bottlenecks and solutions from the Positive Health and Living Environment method to structure outcomes; iii) cognitive mapping, which enables participants to think systemically about causes and consequences of the issue. Four of our Living labs conducted the workshop which provided first insights on the community based co-designed solutions to enhance healthier and more sustainable diets.

Table 3 Summary of key recommendations from FEAST work package 3.

Task	Key Recommendations
3.1 Recommendations for companies:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase transparency on policy positions and environmental compliance. • Ensure nutrition and sustainability commitments are relevant to each country in which they operate. • Eliminate all marketing of unhealthy products to under-18s. • Introduce or expand evidence-based front-of-pack labelling systems such as NutriScore. • Increase the share of healthier and more sustainable products in the company portfolio, including by increasing the proportion of plant-based products. • Commit to making healthy food more affordable.
3.2 Recommendations for governments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthen regulation of food marketing and limit corporate policy influence. • Build public awareness and implement targeted educational campaigns. • Ensure inclusive, equitable, and supportive food policies. • Secure political commitment and long-term funding. • Ensure that sustainable food system policies are explicitly linked to health objectives and promote sustainable diets for public health. • Create platforms for community engagement to discuss food-related issues, policy changes and adapt policies to the unique needs of local communities.
3.3 Recommendations for communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Include community members when designing local solutions to support them towards healthier and more sustainable diets • Community members enjoy co-creating and contribute with fresh and different perspectives relevant to local variation based on own experiences, challenges and existing qualities • Co-create methods should support towards actionable solutions and ownership, through type of tasks and facilitation, but also by including different relevant stakeholders • Key topics in relation to healthier and more sustainable diets such as accessibility, affordability, time, skills and social norms should be added to the discussion if not mentioned by community members

2. Aims

Based on the results of Tasks 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3, we aimed to identify trade-offs and synergies and potential actions across policy domains and governance levels to promote healthier and more sustainable food environments. Potential synergies and trade-offs between nutrition and sustainability were identified.

3. Methods

We used the INFORMAS Healthy Food Environment Policy Index (Food-EPI) as a framework to organise the findings and recommendations from FEAST WP3. This framework aligns with international strategies to reduce non-communicable diseases (NCDs), including the WHO Global Action Plan for the Prevention and Control of NCDs (2013–2020) (18), the World Cancer Research Fund (WCRF), and the International NOURISHING Food Policy Framework for Healthy Diets (19, 20).

Food-EPI includes two key domains:

- **Policy** – focusing on government actions that shape food environments to ensure healthy food choices are accessible, available, and affordable.
- **Infrastructure Support** – encompassing systems and capacities that support the development, implementation, and monitoring of effective policies to prevent obesity and NCDs (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 The Healthy Food Environment Policy Index (Food-EPI)

To synthesise the findings from FEAST Work Package 3 (WP3) and identify synergies, trade-offs and potential actions, we followed a four-step process:

1. Mapping FEAST WP3 Findings to the Food-EPI Domains

The FEAST WP3 tasks were reviewed and their key findings and recommendations were systematically mapped to the domains of the INFORMAS Food Environment Policy Index (Food-EPI). The specific FEAST outputs included:

- **Task 3.1 Report:** *The Business Impact Assessments on Obesity and Sustainability in Belgium, Ireland, and Portugal (DOI)*
- **Country Reports:**
 - Belgium: *BIA-Obesity and BIA-Sustainability (DOI)*
 - Ireland: *BIA-Obesity and BIA-Sustainability (DOI)*
- **Task 3.2 Report:** *Barriers and facilitators for governments to implement actions to improve access to healthy diets from sustainable food systems (submitted for approval)*. This work involved:
 - Mapping of local and national policies against newly proposed FEAST indicators and Food-EPI infrastructure support domains.
- **Task 3.3:** *Outcomes and insights from co-design workshops in FEAST Living Labs*, which gathered stakeholder perspectives on challenges faced by vulnerable groups.

2. Combining FEAST Recommendations

Key findings and recommendations from Tasks 3.1, 3.2, and 3.3 were consolidated during a workshop convened in University College Cork (UCC) with the Food Policy Research Team. A collaborative whiteboard was used to mind-map the findings, this was then shared with partners for review, comment and input. These findings were then categorised according to the Food-EPI policy and infrastructure support domains.

3. Identifying Existing Evidence

Relevant EU-level public policies with direct or indirect influence on food environments were identified for each Food-EPI domain, using the EU Food-EPI evidence document (21). These were further updated through targeted online searches to reflect recent EU policy developments. Where applicable, examples of national and local-level policies and practices from Task 3.2 were also incorporated to contextualise findings within the Food-EPI framework.

4. Visual Mapping (Kumu)

Based on the above mapping, two relationship maps for the policy and infrastructure domains of the FOOD-EPI framework (Figures 2 and 3) were created using *Kumu*. These maps aim to visualise the connections between FEAST WP3 outputs and Food-EPI domains.

Figure 2 and Figure 3 illustrate how FEAST findings align with Food-EPI policy and infrastructure domains, integrating EU-level policy evidence and showcasing good practice examples from national and local contexts across participating FEAST countries where appropriate (Supplementary table A provides full details of these policy and good practice examples).

4. Findings

Previous research at the European Union (EU) level showed that there is much potential for the EU to improve its policies influencing food environments (22). Djojoseparto et al (2022) identified strategic priority actions focused on improving food environments which are required to reduce obesity and NCDs in the EU (22). Further Pineda et al (2022) provided an ‘upstream’ perspective of the policies and infrastructure *support systems* that influence the food environments and dietary choices, for the prevention of obesity and NCDs in 11 European countries (23). The process of consultation with experts allowed an accurate picture of policy action and gaps and helped identify relevant and feasible policy actions for the improvement of food environments across European countries.

The mapping of FEAST recommendations against the Food-EPI policy domains reveals a range of newly identified opportunities and challenges in transforming food environments across the EU. Drawing from the EU-level policy evidence (21), national practices (24), and FEAST findings in partner countries, the relationship maps developed for FEAST D3.3 (Figure 2 and Figure 3) illustrate how strategic policy alignment can support healthier and more sustainable food systems at the policy and infrastructure domains. Here we provide a domain-by-domain narrative summary of insights, actions, synergies and trade-offs in each Food EPI domain and summarised in Table 4 and Table 5.

4.1 Food-EPI Policy Domains

4.1.1 Food composition

Current EU and national efforts to reformulate food products show promising developments, especially in reducing added sugars and nutrients of concern (25,26). Since April 2021, all Member States have implemented a legal limit on industrially produced trans fats in food due to EU Regulation 2019/649 adopted by the Commission in April 2019 (27). Countries like Ireland and Portugal have taken proactive steps through dedicated strategies and reformulation initiatives. For example, Portugal’s Integrated Strategy for the Promotion of Healthy Eating (EIPAS) adopts a cross-sectoral approach to improve food environments and consumer health (28), while Ireland’s Food Reformulation Roadmap 2021–2025 outlines specific targets to reduce salt, sugar, and saturated fat in processed foods (25). These initiatives highlight the potential for coordinated action to improve product composition.

However, tensions remain between the synergies and trade-offs. For example, reformulated products may face challenges in terms of consumer acceptance, taste, and production costs. Strengthening commitments and setting nutrient targets across all Member States can help address public health concerns in relation to the drivers of poor diets and improve compliance with sustainability targets, thus driving progress towards healthier and more sustainable food environments.

4.2.2 Food Labelling

The mapping reveals that while several regulations exist around nutrition and health claims such as the Regulation (EU) No 1169/2011 (29) on the provision of food information to consumers, the implementation of clear, front-of-pack labelling (FOPL) remains disparate across Europe, and a standardised approach to FOPL is absent. Improving transparency through standardised, easy-to-understand labelling presents an opportunity to empower consumers in making healthier food

choices. Nevertheless, potential trade-offs exist, particularly related to resistance from food industry stakeholders and the challenge of harmonising FOPL approaches at the EU level.

4.2.3. Food provision

Industrial agriculture, incentivised (sometimes perversely) supply chains, and insufficient environmental safeguards continue to constrain efforts to build healthier and more resilient food environments. The dominance of large-scale, incentivised food production systems limits local autonomy and restricts access to fresh, nutritious, and culturally appropriate foods—challenges that were repeatedly highlighted by stakeholders across FEAST partner countries during Task 3.2 and the workshops in tasks 3.3 with vulnerable groups. These structural barriers weaken the resilience of food environments and contribute to persistent inequalities in diet and health outcomes.

Despite these challenges, several initiatives have been undertaken—such as the EU Action Plan on Childhood Obesity 2014-2020 (30) and the European Fighting Obesity through Offer and Demand (FOOD) Programme (31) at European level. At the national level, Ireland’s Healthy Workplaces 2021–2025 strategy (32), under the Healthy Ireland Framework, includes an action to develop standards for healthy food in workplace canteens across all sectors, with a phased roll-out planned for the public sector. At the regional level, several countries are taking strategic steps toward healthier food environments. In Austria, the Regionaler Strukturplan Gesundheit für Niederösterreich (33) integrates healthy nutrition into healthcare services, emphasizing prevention, regional food supply, and community-based health promotion. Similarly, Belgium’s Good Food 2 Strategy (2022–2030) in the Brussels-Capital Region promotes a shift toward healthier, more sustainable, and inclusive food systems (34). It focuses on improving food quality, reducing waste, and supporting local food production and consumption, aligning with broader environmental, health, and social objectives. These demonstrate the potential for positive change and transformation. Further, opportunities arise for public procurement which remains a largely incentivising policy lever for advancing both health and sustainability objectives.

To address these issues, actions are needed to shorten supply chains by supporting local and small-scale food producers and by incentivising publicly funded institutions—such as schools, hospitals, and government bodies—to source food locally. These settings offer a powerful opportunity to shape dietary habits, especially among children and other vulnerable populations. Strengthening and aligning public procurement policies could drive demand for healthier and more sustainable food options, while also supporting regional economies.

Such measures present important synergies: equitable food provision policies can help address social inequalities, enhance community food security, and contribute to broader environmental goals by reducing the carbon footprint associated with long-distance food transport. Moreover, integrating health, equity, and sustainability in procurement practices can reinforce public trust and stimulate positive food system transformation.

Nonetheless, these opportunities come with trade-offs. Budgetary constraints at EU, national, and local levels may limit the ability to implement and scale up such policies. Furthermore, effective change will require cross-sectoral coordination, which can be complex and resource-intensive, particularly when navigating diverse institutional mandates and regulatory frameworks.

4.2.4. Food Promotion

Despite growing awareness of the harmful impacts of unhealthy food marketing on children, current EU-level measures remain inadequate. Instruments like the Audiovisual Media Services (AVMS) Directive (35) and various voluntary initiatives have proven insufficient to protect children from the

widespread promotion of unhealthy foods. As highlighted through FEAST WP3 research and previous EU action plans—such as the EU Action Plan on Childhood Obesity (30), and the Joint Action Best ReMaP (36)—progress in curbing these marketing practices has been fragmented.

Children across Europe continue to be routinely exposed to persuasive advertising for foods high in sugar, salt, and unhealthy fats, particularly through digital and broadcast media. While voluntary industry pledges and joint initiatives provide a starting point, they lack the enforcement and consistency needed to achieve meaningful change. The persistent gaps in policy implementation underscore the urgent need for stricter, binding regulations that explicitly limit unhealthy food marketing to minors. This has been highlighted in the outputs from FEAST task 3.2, and task 3.3 whilst simultaneously, support for these policy initiatives have been highlighted in FEAST WP2.

The pathway forward lies in shifting from voluntary to mandatory regulation of food marketing, particularly across digital and broadcast channels. This call to action is backed not only by public health evidence but also by strong public support, as documented in FEAST Work Package 2. Policies that protect children’s health enjoy high levels of acceptability among citizens and can strengthen public trust in government efforts to promote healthier food environments.

There are notable synergies to be gained from adopting stricter regulations. Such policies align with global best practices, including WHO recommendations, and contribute to broader efforts to improve population health and reduce childhood obesity. Moreover, robust marketing restrictions support wider food policy goals by reducing the commercial drivers of unhealthy diets.

However, key trade-offs and challenges remain. Voluntary codes continue to lack effective monitoring and enforcement mechanisms, and industry lobbying often poses significant resistance to stronger regulation. Overcoming these barriers will require coordinated political will, transparent policy design, and clear accountability structures.

Ultimately, safeguarding children from harmful marketing practices is both a public health imperative and a socially supported objective—one that must be met with decisive, mandatory action.

4.2.5. Food in Retail

Retail environments play a critical role in shaping dietary behaviours, influencing what foods people see, choose, and ultimately consume. Yet, in many parts of the EU, these environments remain heavily saturated with the marketing and promotion of unhealthy food products, while access to affordable, nutritious options is often limited—particularly in lower-income or underserved areas.

To address this imbalance, tools such as the BIA-Obesity and BIA-Sustainability assessments have been developed and applied in countries like Belgium and Ireland. These tools provide structured frameworks to assess the nutrition and sustainability commitments of major food retailers and manufacturers. When implemented effectively, they offer a promising approach to improving accountability and encouraging more responsible retail practices. However, realising the full potential of these tools requires more than voluntary assessments.

To drive meaningful change, these efforts must transition into mandatory frameworks that require transparent reporting and compliance with scientifically validated standards for both nutrition and sustainability. Transforming voluntary corporate commitments into mandatory, measurable policy instruments is critical for closing implementation gaps and ensuring private sector accountability in building healthier, more sustainable food environments. Multinational corporations, which dominate the EU's retail and food supply landscape, must be held accountable through transparent targets and robust regulatory frameworks. Without enforceable standards, efforts to improve retail environments risk remaining inconsistent and piecemeal. FEAST identifies this as one of the key recommendations from Task 3.1 highlighting the necessity to hold large food corporations accountable.

At the same time, the global nature of supply chains and intense market competition create significant challenges for standardising and enforcing such practices across Member States. These systemic barriers highlight the need for coordinated EU-level action that combines policy incentives, regulatory measures, and public monitoring to create healthier, more equitable food retail environments.

4.2.6. Food Trade and Investment

Trade and investment agreements play a pivotal role in shaping the national and regional policy space, including the capacity of governments to implement nutrition-sensitive food policies. While these frameworks can support economic integration and development, they often come with constraints that limit public health regulation—particularly in the area of food environments.

Across the EU, many existing free trade agreements (FTAs) and global trade structures tend to favour corporate interests, making it more difficult for governments to enact ambitious policies aimed at improving population nutrition and sustainability of food systems. The dominance of multinational food corporations in trade negotiations amplifies this challenge, creating inherent tensions between commercial agendas and public health goals.

Nevertheless, promising examples are emerging. Ireland's 2022–2026 Trade Strategy (37), for instance, explicitly incorporates health impact assessments as part of its approach to trade policy. This model demonstrates how health considerations can be embedded into broader economic frameworks and offers a practical example for other Member States and the EU more broadly.

To ensure that trade and investment agreements do not undermine national efforts to promote healthier, sustainable and equitable food environments, governments must act proactively. This includes conducting health impact assessments during trade negotiations and explicitly safeguarding the policy space for public health and nutrition within these agreements. Without such safeguards, there is a risk that governments may face legal or political obstacles when attempting to introduce measures like front-of-pack labelling, food marketing restrictions, or sustainability-focused procurement policies.

There are important synergies to be gained from aligning trade policy with public health, sustainability, and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). A more integrated approach to trade can help mitigate the negative impacts of global supply chains, support regional food systems, and foster long-term resilience.

However, key trade-offs and tensions persist. Trade liberalisation may conflict with efforts to regulate unhealthy food marketing or prioritise local procurement. Moreover, political sensitivity around trade negotiations and the strong lobbying power of multinational corporations continue to pose significant barriers to reform. These challenges were highlighted in the interviews with key stakeholders in FEAST task 3.2 where we sought to identify barriers and enablers to developing and implementing action at the local level.

Ultimately, addressing these challenges will require stronger political will, cross-sectoral collaboration, and a commitment to placing public health and sustainability at the centre of trade and investment policy design.

4.2.7. Food Prices

Affordability continues to be one of the most pressing barriers to healthy and sustainable eating, particularly among low-income households across the EU. This was highlighted during the interviews in task 3.2, and it is also an issue which arose in the workshops for FEAST task 3.3. Despite growing awareness of the health consequences of poor diets, many individuals and families are simply unable to afford nutritious food options. This affordability gap is a key structural factor driving inequalities in diet-related health outcomes.

Mapping existing food environment policies highlights several promising approaches to address this challenge. Subsidies for healthier and more sustainable foods—such as fruits, vegetables, and whole grains—have been implemented in some contexts and show positive effects in shifting consumption patterns. Similarly, taxes on unhealthy foods, including sugar-sweetened beverages and ultra-processed products, have been introduced with the aim of discouraging their consumption (38, 39).

These price-based policy instruments can be effective tools to influence dietary behaviour. However, their design and implementation must be carefully considered to avoid unintended consequences. For instance, taxes without adequate compensatory measures—such as subsidies or targeted support—can be regressive, placing a disproportionate burden on low-income consumers. In the broader context of economic hardship, inflation, and rising living costs, the risk of exacerbating food insecurity through poorly designed fiscal policies becomes even more acute.

To ensure equitable outcomes, governments should adopt comprehensive strategies that combine taxes on unhealthy and unsustainable products with subsidies and supports that enhance access to affordable, nutritious and more sustainable food. These policies can also be aligned with agricultural and food provision systems to promote the availability of healthy foods and support sustainable production practices.

There are important synergies to be realised. Well-designed fiscal measures can reduce health inequalities, support vulnerable populations, and strengthen the link between public health, environmental sustainability and food system policy. Integrating these tools with existing frameworks e.g. school food programmes, public procurement strategies, and local food initiatives can enhance their impact.

Nevertheless, these approaches are not without trade-offs. Fiscal policies often face political resistance, particularly from industry stakeholders and segments of the public wary of new taxes. To succeed, such interventions must be accompanied by strong public engagement, clear communication of health and sustainability benefits, and evidence-informed policy design.

Addressing food affordability through price-based interventions is both necessary and feasible—but must be implemented with care to ensure that the most vulnerable populations are protected and empowered to make healthier and more sustainable food choices.

Table 4 Summary of Insights, Actions, Synergies, and Trade-offs by Food-EPI Policy Domain

Food-EPI Domain	Insights	Actions	Synergies	Trade-offs/Tensions
Food Composition	EU and national reformulation initiatives exist, but vary in ambition and enforcement. Italy and Portugal show leadership.	Set nutrient-specific reformulation targets; enforce product composition standards.	National and EU efforts can be aligned to reinforce reformulation; supports health and sustainability.	Taste, cost, and acceptance of reformulated products; industry resistance.
Food Labelling	Front-of-pack labelling is inconsistent across the EU; Belgium presents a good practice example.	Standardise and mandate transparent front-of-pack labelling across Member States.	Clear labelling enhances consumer choice and complements public education.	Industry concerns over branding; lack of harmonisation across countries.
Food Promotion	Unhealthy food promotion to children persists despite existing action plans and voluntary initiatives.	Implement mandatory restrictions on unhealthy food marketing, especially to children.	Marketing restrictions support broader public health goals and child protection.	Weak enforcement; voluntary approaches lack effectiveness; industry opposition.
Food Prices	Healthy food affordability is a major barrier, especially for low-income populations.	Introduce taxes on unhealthy and unsustainable foods and subsidies for healthier options.	Subsidy and tax instruments can promote equity and link to agricultural policies.	Potential regressive effects; political resistance; economic instability complicates pricing strategies.
Food Provision	School and public food programmes have potential, but implementation is uneven.	Improve food standards and expand healthy and sustainable food provision in schools and public settings.	Provision programmes support vulnerable populations and local food systems.	Budget and coordination challenges; inconsistent standards; food waste not fully addressed.
Food Retail	Retail environments often promote unhealthy and unsustainable food; some countries use accountability tools like BIA-Obesity.	Promote healthy and sustainable retail practices and evaluate food company performance with transparency tools.	Retail accountability aligns with health and sustainability goals and supports regulation.	Globalised supply chains hinder national regulation; corporate influence remains strong.
Food Trade and Investment	Trade agreements can restrict national nutrition policies; commercial interests dominate.	Conduct health and sustainability impact assessments and protect nutrition and sustainability policy space in trade agreements.	Trade strategies can align economic, health and sustainability goals if healthier and more sustainable diets/food systems are prioritized.	Health and sustainability goals may conflict with trade liberalisation; enforcement of nutrition and sustainability protections is weak.

4.3 Food EPI Infrastructure Support Domains

The key findings across the infrastructure support domains of the Food Environment Policy Index (Food-EPI) are synthesized in the following sections. Drawing on findings from FEAST WP 3.1 and WP3.2 and from recent European-level policy mapping (JPI PEN) (21) we summarise insights, recommended actions, potential synergies, and trade-offs to support improved cohesiveness for food environment policies across the Food EPI infrastructure support domains.

4.3.1 Leadership

European-level leadership in policy is underpinned by strategic frameworks and documents, such as the European Commission's reflection paper towards a sustainable Europe by 2030 (40), European Action supporting the 2030 Agenda and the SDGs among others (41). These have provided a foundation for member states to adopt integrated approaches. Countries like Ireland and Portugal exemplify this leadership through national strategies that align food and health objectives. In Ireland, the Healthy Ireland Implementation Plan 2023-2027 (42) aims to improve healthy behaviours, reduce health inequalities, and prevent chronic disease, help people manage chronic conditions as well as create environments that make the healthy choice the easier choice. The Healthy Eating Active Living Implementation (HEAL) Plan 2023-2027 (43) mobilise the health services to improve health and wellbeing by increasing the levels of physical activity, healthy diet and healthier weight across service users, staff and the population as a whole, with a focus on families and children. Complementing these health strategies, Ireland's *Food Vision 2030* (44) sets out a long-term political commitment to become a global leader in sustainable food systems by producing safe, nutritious, and high-value food while safeguarding natural and cultural resources while contributing to rural communities and the national economy. In Portugal the Integrated Strategy for Promoting Healthy Eating (EIPAS) (45) and the National Program for Promoting Healthy Eating (PNPAS) (46) prioritize public health through nutrition-focused measures, including promoting Mediterranean diets, maternal-child nutrition during the first 1,000 days, and improving access to dietary information.

To strengthen leadership further, action is needed to incorporate social goals—such as reducing inequality and expanding access to sustainable food—into overarching food policy agendas. Promoting transparency and ensuring public access to information are also crucial for building legitimacy and public trust.

Opportunities for synergy exist in aligning food policies with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and embedding them into local economic and community development plans. Additionally, integrating nutrition and environmental goals, such as promoting healthier and more sustainable diets, supports a joined-up approach to health and climate policy.

However, the degree of political will and prioritisation varies across jurisdictions. Moreover, integrating food quality objectives into policy may sometimes conflict with dominant economic or industrial agendas resulting in trade-offs at different levels. At the local level, a lack of financial or administrative capacity can further hinder the implementation of transformative policies or national goals.

4.3.2 Governance

The governance landscape at the EU level is supported by a clear legal framework and instruments for transparency, such as EU Treaties (e.g. Treaty on the Union¹²³ (47) and the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (48)) and the Transparency Register (49). There are also multiple initiatives aimed at strengthening accountability and benchmarking within the food policy arena. The [European Food Safety Authority \(EFSA\)](#) plays a key role in the development of food and nutrition policies by evaluating scientific evidence and providing risk assessments. These assessments inform policies aimed at ensuring food safety, promoting healthy diets, and addressing public health concerns related to food and nutrition. In addition, to these EU-level efforts, countries like Belgium and Ireland are advancing food governance at the city level. For example, Brussels' Climate Plan 2 (50) stands out for its strong emphasis on transparency throughout the policy process. It ensures public access to reports and incorporates a Local Climate Assembly. In Cork City, supported by Cork City Council and the Local Economic and Community Plan, the Cork Food Policy Council are developing a food strategy for the city (51).

Further, taxation and subsidy measures are inconsistent and lack clear nutrition alignment (e.g. liberalisation of sugar markets, minimal disincentives for unhealthy foods). While these measures are inconsistent, results from FEAST work package 2, which assessed public perception of various policy options ([10.5281/zenodo.12704570](#)), indicate high levels of support for policies to support creating healthier and more sustainable food environments in Europe.

Moving forward, action is required to support regulatory or hybrid governance models for Member States, particularly those that facilitate both public oversight and private sector engagement. Promoting corporate accountability, especially through sustainability metrics and global standards, is another critical step. Such measures can generate synergies by enhancing transparency, improving trust in institutions, and encouraging corporate practices that align with health goals. However, a key challenge and trade-off lies in the reliance on voluntary measures, which often lack sufficient enforcement mechanisms. Additionally, corporate lobbying can delay or weaken public interest regulations, limiting their potential impact.

4.3.3 Monitoring and Intelligence

Monitoring systems are well-established across Europe, but their scope and effectiveness vary significantly between countries and policy areas. Key instruments such as Eurostat, the European Community Health Indicators (ECH), the WHO's Childhood Obesity Surveillance Initiative (COSI), the Health Behaviour in School-aged Children (HBSC) surveys, and the European Commission's NOPA (Nutrition, Obesity and Physical Activity) database provide valuable datasets. However, these systems are often fragmented, lack integration, and fail to capture all dimensions of the food environment, particularly in relation to commercial food practices and equity outcomes.

At the national level, some countries operate systems that track compliance in targeted areas such as, food composition regulations, and food environment including food safety. Yet, the coverage and enforcement of such systems remain variable. Ireland, for instance, implements comprehensive monitoring and surveillance through the Food Safety Authority of Ireland (FSAI), working in collaboration with official agencies such as the Health Service Executive (HSE), the Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine, and the Sea Fisheries Protection Authority. Their efforts include

regular assessments of microbiological safety, genetically modified content, food irradiation, and labelling compliance. Similarly, Austria’s Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES) monitors a wide range of food environment indicators and plays a key role in promoting healthier food systems at the national level.

There is a need for action to expand, strengthen, and integrate these monitoring frameworks. Establishing benchmarking systems with mandatory reporting requirements would improve consistency, comparability, and accountability across the EU and beyond. These actions would support more effective policy evaluation and learning.

Opportunities for synergy lie in linking nutrition, public health, and environmental datasets to develop integrated metrics that better reflect the complexity of food systems. Such approaches would enable more holistic and evidence-based policymaking and foster greater policy coherence across sectors. Nonetheless, trade-offs must be carefully managed. The administrative burden of comprehensive monitoring can strain the capacities of national and local authorities, potentially undermining data quality and compliance. Additionally, tensions may arise between the imperative for data transparency and the need to safeguard proprietary or sensitive personal information, particularly when engaging with the private sector.

Cross-sectoral coordination is essential to advance food system transformation. Greater alignment between nutrition, public health, healthcare, agriculture, and trade policy can reduce fragmentation and conflicting goals. Instruments such as the EU’s Common Agricultural Policy Strategic Plans and EFSA’s scientific assessments provide key entry points for embedding integrated nutrition–sustainability metrics that guide funding, regulation, and monitoring.

4.3.4 Funding and Resources

EU and national governments have made substantial investments in nutrition and food environment research. For example, at the European level programmes such as Horizon Europe, ERA4Health, and FutureFoods (among others) reflect the increasing recognition of the sector’s significance. Specifically, Horizon Europe Cluster 6 will serve the new Commission priorities for 2024-2029 with a focus on “Sustaining our quality of life: food security, water and nature” and “A new plan for Europe’s sustainable prosperity and competitiveness. Dedicated budget lines—such as those for “population nutrition”—further underscore this growing policy and funding focus.

However, to catalyse transformative change in food systems, increased and better-targeted funding is essential. Such investment is particularly needed to support initiatives that improve equitable access to healthier and more sustainable diets. As evidenced from FEAST task 3.3, and previously stated, it remains that from a community perspective, cost, affordability and availability of healthier and more sustainable food is a significant barrier. Insights from FEAST Task 3.2 highlighted EU funding programmes and collaborative networks as critical enablers of regional and local food system innovation. Nationally, initiatives including Austria’s Fonds Gesundes Österreich (FGÖ) (52), Belgium’s Climate Project Call (53) and Ireland’s Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine funding call (54), provide financial support to projects aiming to promote sustainable practices, such as agriculture, climate resilience and healthy lifestyles. Local governments also emphasised their capacity to drive

sustainable change, provided they are supported by appropriate financial instruments and policy frameworks.

To unlock these opportunities, economic incentives must be strategically designed to promote healthier dietary patterns and more sustainable food production. Aligning financial flows with public health, environmental sustainability, and economic resilience can support systemic reform and long-term impact.

Investments in research and innovation offer a high return by generating the evidence base needed to design, test, and scale effective interventions. Funding mechanisms that support cross-sectoral integration can drive progress across multiple policy goals.

Despite these opportunities, challenges remain. Nutrition and food system initiatives frequently compete with other high-priority areas—such as climate adaptation, healthcare, social protection, or, more recently, defence—for finite public resources. In addition, many funding models are short-term or project-based, which can limit the capacity to sustain and scale successful interventions over time. A shift toward long-term, integrated financing is needed to support meaningful, durable transformation.

4.3.5 Platforms for Interaction

Numerous platforms facilitate policy coordination and stakeholder interaction, such as the EU Platform for Diet and Physical Activity and the Healthy Diet for Healthy Life (HDHL). Networks like the European Public Health Alliance (EPHA) and the NCD Alliance contribute to cross-sectoral collaboration.

To maximise the potential of these platforms, it is important to foster stronger coordination across food, health, environment, and trade sectors. Interaction between local, regional, national, and EU-level actors must also be enhanced to ensure vertical alignment and local relevance. In Austria, the Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES) is a public institution that works on behalf of several ministries. It operates the Service Center for Sustainable Food and Nutrition Systems, which works with ministries to support the transformation towards a more sustainable food system in Austria (55). The EcoPlus Lebensmittel-Cluster Niederösterreich serves mostly as a platform for interaction between government and the commercial food sector (56). However, while examples of platforms for interaction between formal government (all levels) structures and key stakeholder exist, structure for interaction with public and civic societies are sparse. As highlighted in FEAST task 3.2, the potential of public engagement and civil society advocacy to drive change, remains underutilized in promoting demand for healthier, equitable, and more sustainable food environments. This limits bottom-up pressure on policymakers and industry actors.

Effective platforms for interaction across, within and between all sectors has the potential to enable more efficient policy development and implementation. Inclusive platforms can amplify the voices of diverse stakeholders, especially civil society and marginalised communities. Investing in strategic public awareness campaigns that inform citizens and empower communities to advocate for healthier and more sustainable food environments was highlighted as an action in FEAST task 3.2 along with

developing clear and transparent structures for citizens to communicate with policymakers. The Cork Food Policy Council provides an example of good practice, in that it actively seeks public input (from all citizens, not just specific stakeholders or groups) on its strategy, and it has direct lines of communication to the local government (51).

Nonetheless, fragmentation and political complexity often undermine these platforms' effectiveness. Bureaucratic silos, institutional inertia as well as corporate/regulatory capture continue to pose barriers to fast, integrated action.

4.3.6 Health in-All Policies

The EU has made progress in embedding health within broader policy domains through instruments such as the EU Treaties (47, 48). At the local level, plans such as the Cork City Development Plan 2022-2028 in Ireland (57) and at a regional level the Austrian Regionaler Strukturplan Gesundheit für Niederösterreich incorporate health outcomes into broader planning processes (58).

Further steps are needed to fully integrate health considerations into environmental, economic, and food-related policies. Health Impact Assessments (HIAs) can play a crucial role in ensuring that health is considered in decision-making across all relevant sectors.

Synergies emerge when health goals are aligned with climate action, equity, and sustainability, creating a strong case for cross-sector collaboration. Encouraging corporate adherence to global standards such as those set by the WHO can also enhance the reach and impact of policy interventions.

Despite these opportunities, integrating health across multiple policy areas remains complex. Resistance from sectors not traditionally aligned with public health objectives—such as agriculture or trade—can impede progress and create institutional friction.

Table 5 Summary of Insights, Actions, Synergies, and Trade-offs by Food-EPI Infrastructure Support Domains

Food-EPI Domain	Insights	Actions	Synergies	Trade-offs
Leadership	Strong EU-level strategies and frameworks; national integration (e.g., Ireland, Portugal).	Advance social and sustainability objectives; increase transparency and public information access.	Links to SDGs and local plans enhance coherence; align health and climate goals.	Varying political will; local capacity/resource challenges.
Governance	Established EU legal/transparency frameworks; emerging corporate accountability mechanisms.	Support hybrid governance models; promote corporate sustainability metrics.	Transparency and global reporting standards build trust and accountability.	Voluntary measures may lack enforcement; risk of industry pushback.
Monitoring and Intelligence	Existing monitoring frameworks vary; some focus on schools, composition, advertising.	Expand/integrate systems; implement benchmarking with mandatory reporting.	Integrated systems enable holistic policy decisions across domains.	Data burden may reduce compliance; privacy vs. transparency.
Funding and Resources	Targeted EU/national funding exists; dedicated budgets for nutrition-related goals.	Increase funding for transformation; align economic incentives with diet goals.	Funding and research inform scalable, multisectoral interventions.	Funding competition across sectors; risk of short-termism.

Mapping and identification of policies for healthy and sustainable food systems

Platforms for Interaction	Multiple platforms exist for coordination across sectors; some support cross-silo collaboration.	Foster intersectoral coordination; strengthen EU-local level interaction.	Cross-sector platforms improve policy alignment and stakeholder engagement.	Bureaucratic silos and fragmentation reduce effectiveness.
Health-in-All Policies	Legislative tools embed health in policy; local plans include health outcomes.	Integrate health in all policy domains; apply Health Impact Assessments.	Co-benefits from aligning health with climate, sustainability, equity.	Alignment complexity; resistance from non-health sectors.

Figure 2 FEAST outputs mapped to the Food-EPI Policy domains, EU policy evidence and good practice examples identified at national level in selected FEAST countries

Mapping and identification of policies for healthy and sustainable food systems

Figure 3 FEAST outputs mapped to the Food-EPI Infrastructure Support domains, EU policy evidence and good practice examples identified at national level in selected FEAST countries

5. Implications for Food Environment Transformation

The EU, its Member States as well as its local governments hold significant capacity to shape food environments that are **equitable, health-promoting** and **sustainable**. Achieving healthier and more sustainable food environments across Europe requires coordinated action by a diverse set of actors. Each actor group — from supranational institutions to local communities — has a distinct yet interdependent role in shaping the systems, policies, and everyday environments that influence dietary behaviour and food security and equitable access to healthier and more sustainable food. Existing policy instruments—including the EU Vision for Agriculture and Food (59) the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) (60), EU and Member State-level initiatives—provide a solid foundation for transforming the food environment. However, realising this potential demands strategic investment in political will, enforcement mechanisms, and multi-level coordination. Following the exploration of the trade-offs and synergies in potential actions to promote healthier and more sustainable food environments in the previous sections, Table 6 takes a multi-level governance lense to outline the implications for key actor groups based on the findings of FEAST WP3 and the INFORMAS Food-EPI framework.

Table 6 Multi-level Governance lense: Actor-Level Implications for Food Environment Transformation

Actor Group & related	Key Roles	Key Implications	Potential Synergies	Potential Trade-offs
EU Institutions	Set regulatory frameworks, funding priorities, and cross-country coordination	Legislate binding standards; integrate health and sustainability in trade; fund innovation; harmonise monitoring	Policy harmonisation across Member States; collective impact on food environments	Complex coordination across countries; potential resistance from Member States; corporate/regulatory capture
National Governments	Translate EU frameworks into national laws and coordinate intersectoral policy	Enforce regulations; align health and food systems; provide funding to local levels	Integrated strategies improve coherence between health, environment, and food systems	Political resistance to regulation; competing priorities across ministries; corporate/regulatory capture
Sub-national / Local Governments	Implement local food policies, manage public procurement, engage communities	Procure healthy, sustainable food; support local producers; embed food goals in planning	Local procurement supports community health, economy, and climate goals	Limited resources and capacity; risk of inconsistent implementation
Civil Society and Citizens	Hold governments and corporations accountable; raise awareness and advocate	Advocate for equity and transparency; participate in governance; mobilise public support	Increased legitimacy and responsiveness of food policy; public support for reform	Unequal access to participation; limited influence over systemic change
Private Sector	Shape food supply, marketing, and retail; implement reform and accountability measures	Reformulate products; end harmful marketing; increase transparency and accountability	Healthier products and reputational benefits; alignment with global standards	Profit margins may conflict with health/environment goals; resistance to regulation

Academia and Research Institutions	Generate evidence, support evaluation, build capacity, and inform policy	Evaluate policies; develop monitoring tools; support implementation and cross-sector learning	Evidence-informed policy; enhanced cross-sector learning and innovation	Research translation gaps; funding shortfalls; limited influence without policy uptake
------------------------------------	--	---	---	--

5.1 Opportunities for Nutrition–Sustainability Synergies

This section summarises the opportunities for nutrition-sustainability synergies and outlines the potential mechanisms to maximise the success of these synergies.

Efforts to transform food environments should aim to maximise the synergies between nutrition and sustainability goals. These synergies are maximised when policies are designed to:

- Operate across **multiple levels of governance** and engage a broad range of actors, including public institutions, civil society, and the private sector.
- **Integrate equity considerations**, ensuring that interventions address affordability, cultural relevance, and access for vulnerable populations.
- Emphasize **transparency and corporate accountability**, while supporting the development of **resilient local food systems** that contribute to both environmental and social wellbeing.

Such integrated approaches not only have the potential to produce better outcomes, but also build greater public trust and political legitimacy for policy interventions.

5.2 Addressing Structural Trade-offs

Despite the potential for synergy, a number of **structural trade-offs** must be recognised and addressed to achieve inclusive and effective transformation:

- **Economic inequality** continues to be a significant barrier. Without targeted supports, lower-income populations are often unable to access healthier and more sustainable food options, exacerbating existing health and social disparities.
- **Global trade dynamics** can undermine national or local efforts to support sustainable agriculture, protect food sovereignty, or regulate unhealthy and unsustainable food products. Trade liberalisation may conflict with health-oriented or environmentally conscious policies unless safeguards are built in.
- **Social constraints**—including time poverty, limited cooking or food literacy, and caregiving responsibilities—also influence dietary behaviours and must be factored into policy design. Interventions that assume a high level of individual capacity or time availability risk deepening inequalities.

6. Conclusion

The path toward healthier, more sustainable food environments requires careful navigation of power dynamics, incentives, disincentives, opportunities and tradeoffs. Many approaches to support this transition exist—but activating them requires bold, coordinated action grounded in equity and accountability. For example, cities like Cork and Ghent (among others) demonstrate the transformative potential of place-based food systems in advancing both nutrition and sustainability goals. These urban initiatives showcase how local governance can drive integrated food system change through community engagement, procurement, and planning. By leveraging synergies for nutrition and sustainability and balancing trade-offs, the EU, member states and local governments can make meaningful progress toward reducing diet-related NCDs and achieving global nutrition and climate targets. With strategic action, Europe can move toward a food system that is not only healthier and more sustainable but also more just and resilient.

References

1. Rutter H. The complex systems challenge of obesity. *Clin Chem*. 2018;64(1):44-46. doi: 10.1373/clinchem.2017.272831.
2. Deliens T, Clarys P, De Bourdeaudhuij I, Deforche B. Determinants of eating behaviour in university students: A qualitative study using focus group discussions. *BMC public health*. 2014;14(1):53. doi: 10.1186/1471-2458-14-53.
3. Kabir A, Miah S, Islam A. Factors influencing eating behavior and dietary intake among resident students in a public university in Bangladesh: A qualitative study. *PLoS One*. 2018;13(6). doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0198801.
4. EUFIC. The factors that influence our food choices. 2006. Available from <https://www.eufic.org/en/healthy-living/article/the-determinants-of-food-choice>. Accessed June 2025.
5. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. Influencing food environments for healthy diets. 2016. Available from <https://openknowledge.fao.org/items/060ce716-3d8b-4574-9857-dc38252fc283>. Accessed June 2025.
6. Swinburn B, Sacks G, Vandevijvere S, et al. INFORMAS (International Network for Food and Obesity/non-communicable diseases Research, Monitoring and Action Support): Overview and key principles. *Obesity Reviews*. 2013;14(S1):1-12. doi: 10.1111/obr.12087.
7. European Commission. Farm to Fork Strategy. For a fair, healthy, environmentally-friendly food system. 2020. Available from https://food.ec.europa.eu/horizontal-topics/farm-fork-strategy_en. Accessed June 2025.
8. Moodie R, Swinburn B, Richardson J, et al. Childhood obesity – a sign of commercial success, but a market failure. *International Journal of Pediatric Obesity*. 2006;1(3):133-138. doi: 0.1080/17477160600845044
9. World Health Organization. Obesity and Overweight. 2025. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/obesity-and-overweight>. Accessed June 2025.
10. Swinburn B, Vandevijvere S, Kraak V, et al. Monitoring and benchmarking government policies and actions to improve the healthiness of food environments: A proposed Government Healthy Food Environment Policy Index. *Obesity Reviews*. 2013;14(S1):24-37. doi: 10.1111/obr.12073.
11. Story M, Kaphingst KM, Robinson-O'Brien R, Glanz K. Creating healthy food and eating environments: policy and environmental approaches. *Annu Rev Public Health*. 2008;29:253-72. doi: 10.1146/annurev.publhealth.29.020907.090926. PMID: 18031223.
12. Gorski MT, Roberto CA. Public health policies to encourage healthy eating habits: recent perspectives. *J Healthc Leadersh*. 2015 Sep 23;7:81-90. doi: 10.2147/JHL.S69188.
13. Mozaffarian D, Angell SY, Lang T, et al. Role of government policy in nutrition-barriers to and opportunities for healthier eating. *BMJ (Clinical research ed.)*. 2018;361:k2426. doi: 10.1136/bmj.k2426.
14. EUR-Lex. Consolidated version of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union – PART THREE: UNION POLICIES AND INTERNAL ACTIONS – TITLE XIV: PUBLIC HEALTH – Article 168 (ex Article 152 TEC) OJ C 115, 9.5.2008, p. 122-124. Available from <https://op.europa.eu/publication-detail/-/publication/53b9de4b-14dc-485f-902e-17dd58f6891c>. Accessed June 2025.
15. European Commission. Live, work, travel in the EU. EU Health Policy. Overview. Available from https://ec.europa.eu/health/policies/overview_en. Accessed June 2025.
16. European Commission, DG Health and Food Safety. Strategic plan 2016-2020. 2016. Available from https://commission.europa.eu/publications/strategic-plan-2016-2020-health-and-food-safety_en. Accessed June 2025.

17. Breda J, Castro LSN, Whiting S, et al. Towards better nutrition in Europe: Evaluating progress and defining future directions. *Food policy*. 2020;96:101887. doi: 10.1016/j.foodpol.2020.101887.
18. World Health Organization. Global action plan for the prevention and control of noncommunicable diseases 2013-2020. 2013. Available from: https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/94384/9789241506236_eng.pdf;jsessionid=A30D30A6E2EA32BBF4DD006156F48D09?sequence=1. Accessed June 2025.
19. Hawkes C, Jewell J, Allen K. A food policy package for healthy diets and the prevention of obesity and diet-related non-communicable diseases: the NOURISHING framework. *Obes Rev*. 2013;14(S2):159–68.
20. NOURISHING framework. World Cancer Research Fund. 2014. Available from: <https://www.wcrf.org/research-policy/policy/nutrition-policy/nourishing-framework/>. Accessed June 2025.
21. Djojoseparto SK, Kamphuis CBM, Vandevijvere S, Harrington JM and Poelman MP for the Food-EPI project team. JPI-HDHL Policy Evaluation Network. The Healthy Food Environment Policy Index (Food-EPI): European Union. An overview of EU-level policies influencing food environments in EU Member States. Utrecht, Utrecht University 2020.
22. Djojoseparto SK, Kamphuis CBM, Vandevijvere S, Murrin C, Stanley I, Romaniuk P, Harrington JM, Poelman MP; PEN Consortium. Strength of EU-level food environment policies and priority recommendations to create healthy food environments. *Eur J Public Health*. 2022 Jun 1;32(3):504-511. doi: 10.1093/eurpub/ckac010.
23. Pineda, E., Poelman, M.P., Aaspõllu, A., Bica, M., Bouzas, C., Carrano, E., De Miguel-Etayo, P., Djojoseparto, S., Blenkuš, M.G., Graca, P. and Geffert, K., 2022. Policy implementation and priorities to create healthy food environments using the Healthy Food Environment Policy Index (Food-EPI): A pooled level analysis across eleven European countries. *The Lancet Regional Health—Europe*, 23. Doi: 10.1016/j.lanepe.2022.100522
24. Harrington JM, Griffen C, and Vandevijvere S, for the Food EPI project team. The Healthy Food Environment Policy Index (Food-EPI): Evidence document for Ireland 2020. Cork, School of Public Health, University College Cork 2020.
25. Department of Health. A roadmap for food product reformulation in Ireland 2021–2025. Reformulation Sub-Group, Obesity Policy Implementation Oversight Group; 2021. Dublin: Government of Ireland. Available from: <https://www.fsai.ie/getmedia/44c8bf97-35ee-445f-b354-af4de3d57fa9/food-reformulation-roadmap.pdf>
26. Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety, 2011. EU Framework for National Initiatives on Selected Nutrients. High Level Group on Nutrition and Physical Activity. Brussels: European Commission. Available from: https://health.ec.europa.eu/publications/eu-framework-national-initiatives-selected-nutrients_en
27. European Commission, 2019. Commission Regulation (EU) 2019/649 of 24 April 2019 amending Annex III to Regulation (EC) No 1925/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards trans fat, other than trans fat naturally occurring in fat of animal origin. *Official Journal of the European Union*, L 110, pp.17–20. Available from: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2019/649/oj>
28. Directorate-General of Health, 2017. Integrated Strategy for the Promotion of Healthy Eating (EIPAS). Order No. 11418/2017, of 29 December. Lisbon: Ministry of Health, Portuguese Republic.
29. European Parliament and Council. Regulation (EU) No 1169/2011 of 25 October 2011 on the provision of food information to consumers. *Official Journal of the European Union*. 2011;L304:18-63
30. European Commission. EU Action Plan on Childhood Obesity 2014–2020. Brussels: Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety; 2014. Available at: https://health.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2016-11/childhoodobesity_actionplan_2014_2020_en_0.pdf

31. European Commission. European Fighting Obesity through Offer and Demand (FOOD) Programme. Brussels: European Commission; 2012. Available at: <https://www.food-programme.eu/en/>
32. Department of Health. Ireland's Healthy Workplaces 2021–2025 Strategy. Dublin: Government of Ireland; 2021. Available from: <https://www.gov.ie/en/healthy-ireland/publications/healthy-workplace-framework/>
33. Government of Lower Austria. Regional Health Structure Plan for Lower Austria. St. Pölten: Office of the Government of Lower Austria; 2018. Available from: https://www.noel.gv.at/noel/Gesundheitseinrichtungen/Regionaler_Strukturplan_Gesundheit_fuer_Niederosterreich.html
34. Brussels-Capital Region. Good Food 2 Strategy (2022–2030). Brussels: Government of the Brussels-Capital Region; 2022. Available from: https://goodfood.brussels/sites/default/files/inlinefiles/BRO_GoodFood_Strategy_ENGL.pdf
35. European Parliament and Council. Directive (EU) 2018/1808 of 14 November 2018 amending Directive 2010/13/EU on the coordination of certain provisions laid down by law, regulation or administrative action in Member States concerning the provision of audiovisual media services (Audiovisual Media Services Directive). Official Journal of the European Union. 2018;L303:69–92. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2018/1808/oj/eng>
36. Joint Action Best ReMaP (Best Practices in Reducing Marketing Pressure on Children). European Union Health Programme; 2019. Available at: <https://bestremap.eu>
37. Department of Enterprise, Trade and Employment. Trade and Investment Strategy 2022–2026: Value for Ireland, Values for the World. Dublin: Government of Ireland; 2022. Available at: <https://www.gov.ie/en/publication/3b8c0-trade-and-investment-strategy-2022-2026-value-for-ireland-values-for-the-world/>
38. Teagasc. Sustainability in Agriculture: The Science & Evidence [Conference proceedings]. Ashtown (Dublin): Teagasc; 2024. Available at: <https://www.teagasc.ie/media/website/publications/2024/Sustainability-in-Agriculture-The-science-and-the-Evidence-Conference-proceedings.pdf>
39. Global Nutrition Report. 2022 Global Nutrition Report: Stronger commitments for greater action. Global Nutrition Report; 2022. Available at: <https://globalnutritionreport.org/reports/2022-global-nutrition-report/>
40. European Commission: Directorate-General for Communication, Towards a sustainable Europe by 2030 – Reflection paper, Publications Office, 2019. Available at: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2775/676251>
41. European Commission. Report from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions – EU Voluntary Review on progress in the implementation of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. COM(2023)700 final. Brussels: European Commission, 2023. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52023DC0700>
42. Health Service Executive. Health Services Healthy Ireland Implementation Plan 2023–2027. Dublin: HSE; 2023. Available from: <https://www.hse.ie/eng/about/who/healthwellbeing/healthy-ireland/hse-health-services-healthy-ireland-implementation-plan-2023-2027.pdf>
43. Health Service Executive. Healthy Eating Active Living (HEAL) Implementation Plan 2023–2027. Dublin: HSE; 2023. Available from: <https://www.hse.ie/eng/about/who/healthwellbeing/our-priority-programmes/heal/the-healthy-eating-active-living-implementation-plan-2023-2027.pdf>
44. Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine. Food Vision 2030 – A World Leader in Sustainable Food Systems. Dublin: Government of Ireland; 2021. Available from: <https://www.gov.ie/en/department-of-agriculture-food-and-the-marine/publications/food-vision-2030-a-world-leader-in-sustainable-food-systems/>

45. Directorate-General of Health (Portugal). *Estratégia Integrada para a Promoção da Alimentação Saudável (EIPAS)*. Despacho no. 11418/2017, de 29 December 2017; Lisbon: Portuguese Republic; 2017.
46. Directorate-General of Health (Portugal). National Program for the Promotion of Healthy Eating (PNPAS). Order No. 404/2012, of 13 January 2012. Lisbon: DGS; 2012. Updated in 2023 for the 2022–2030 phase.
47. European Parliament and Council. Treaty on European Union (Maastricht), 7 February 1992 (consolidated by Treaty of Lisbon, 13 December 2007; effective 1 December 2009). Official Journal C 191/1; L 326/13–45.
48. European Union. Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU). Consolidated version. Official Journal of the European Union, C 202, 7 June 2016, pp. 47–390
49. European Parliament, Council of the European Union & European Commission. Interinstitutional Agreement of 20 May 2021 on a mandatory Transparency Register. Official Journal of the European Union, JOL 207, 2021: OJ L 207/
50. City of Brussels. Climate Plan 2.0 for the territory of the City of Brussels. Adopted 12 December 2022; Brussels: City of Brussels; 2022.
51. Cork Food Policy Council & Cork City Council. Draft Vision for a Sustainable and Healthy Food Strategy for Cork 2025–2030. Cork: Cork City Council; 2025.
52. Fonds Gesundes Österreich (FGÖ). Health Promotion and Primary Prevention: Laws, Funding Programs and Strategic Framework. Vienna: FGÖ; founded 1998 under Health Promotion Act, updated framework programme 2024–2028.
53. City of Brussels. Climate Plan Call for Projects 2025. City of Brussels; launched 1 May 2025. Brussels: City of Brussels; 2025.
54. Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine. Thematic Research Call 2025. Dublin: DAFM; launched 16 April 2025.
55. Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety GmbH (AGES). Health and Food Safety Experts for Austria: One Health Approach, Risk Assessment, Food Chain Control and Applied Research. Vienna: AGES; founded 2002, updated 2024.
56. Ecoplus. Lebensmittel-Cluster Niederösterreich – Overview of the food cluster’s role, reach, Gold Label status, and innovation initiatives. St. Pölten: ecoplus – Niederösterreich’s Wirtschaftsagentur GmbH; ongoing since 2001
57. Cork City Council. Cork City Development Plan 2022–2028. Adopted 10 June 2022; effective 8 August 2022. Cork: Cork City Council; 2022.
58. Office of the Provincial Government of Lower Austria. Regional Health Structural Plan for Lower Austria 2025 – Part 1. St. Pölten: Government of Lower Austria; adopted 17 December 2018.
59. European Commission. Vision for Agriculture and Food. Brussels: European Commission; presented 19 February 2025. Available from: https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/overview-vision-agriculture-food/vision-agriculture-and-food_en
60. European Commission. Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). Brussels: European Commission; updated 2023. Available at: https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/common-agricultural-policy_en

www.feast2030.eu

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

FEAST is co-funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 101060536. Views and opinions expressed are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

UK participant in FEAST (Good Food Oxfordshire) is supported by Innovate UK grant number 10041509 and the Swiss participant in FEAST (FiBL) is supported by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) under contract number 22.00156.